

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH TO TEACHING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

Today, English is being taught in a new way, in new trends. Mastering these techniques is very important in the learning process. In this article we will consider new, modern trends in teaching English.

INTRODUCTION

The topical issue today is how to teach a foreign language to students in modern conditions. The goals and content of education are changing, new approaches and learning technologies are emerging, and the goal of teaching a foreign language today is no longer achievable by simply communicating a certain amount of knowledge that students must memorize and reproduce. Simultaneously with arming with knowledge and on its basis, it is necessary to teach students the methods of cognition and practical activity that mankind has developed.

The study of foreign languages in modern society is becoming an integral part of the professional training of specialists in various fields, and their further career growth may largely depend on the degree of their language training. Learning a foreign language contributes to the development of communicative competence and forms the student's ability to use it as a communication tool. The success of training largely depends on the correct selection of teaching methods¹.

MAIN PART

The variety of methods and ways of mastering a foreign language in a higher educational institution leads to the need for a rational choice of one of them or the optimal combination of complementary methods and technologies, which implies the need to generalize knowledge about the methods and techniques of organizing foreign language communication. Currently, intensive teaching of foreign languages is implemented in various developing, newly created and existing methodological systems. This is due to the variety of specific goals of teaching a foreign language to various contingents of students, as well as the variety of learning conditions.

The case method or the method of specific situations is a method of active problem-situational analysis based on learning by solving specific problems - situations. The immediate goal of the case method is a joint discussion and analysis of a case (events that occurred in a particular

¹ Richards, J.K. and Rogers, T.S. (2016). P.81 "Approaches and methods of teaching languages". Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. P.43

field of activity) by a group of students, the development of a practical solution, followed by an assessment of the proposed algorithms and the choice of the best in the context of the problem posed.

Case - these are events that really happened in a particular field of activity in order to provoke a discussion in the classroom. The case method in teaching English can be used taking into account the specifics of the subject. In order to form the necessary skills and abilities in students in one form or another of foreign language speech activity, as well as linguistic competence at the level determined by the program and standard, an active oral foreign language practice is necessary for each participant in the educational process. Since a foreign language, as an element of culture, functions within a certain culture, it is also about the need to form students' regional competence. In order to form communicative competence outside the language environment, it is necessary to look for ways to include students in an active dialogue of cultures so that they can learn in practice the features of the functioning of the English language in cultures that are new to them².

The case method, which has won a leading position in the modern practice of studying abroad, by developing the mastery of these speech functions, makes it possible to acquire knowledge of a specialty in a foreign language, increase the level of one's professional competence and self-esteem. At the same time, the learning goals defined earlier in the methodology: communicative attitude, language goal, mental and educational goals, etc., remain relevant. The leading role in the theoretical development of the method and its practical application belongs to P. Duff, S. Faltis, J. Heap.

M. Dolgorukov classifies the "case study" method as an "advanced" active learning method. An increase in the student's "baggage" of analyzed cases increases the likelihood of using a ready-made decision scheme for the current situation, forms skills for solving more serious problems. Situational learning teaches the search for and use of knowledge in a dynamic situation, developing the flexibility of thinking.

The use of the case method in English classes in a professional environment pursues two complementary goals, namely: further improvement of communicative competence (linguistic and sociocultural) and the formation of students' professional qualities. Acquaintance with the case (reading a professionally directed text, in which the problem is formulated in the specialty, in the original or with slight reductions and slight adaptation, and subsequent translation), independent search for a solution (internal monologue speech in English), the process of analyzing the situation during the lesson (monologue and dialogic speech, prepared and spontaneous, also in English) are all examples of communicative tasks³.

Classroom communication associated with working on a case, which is characterized by dispute, discussion, argumentation, description, comparison, persuasion and other speech acts, trains the skill of developing the right strategy for speech behavior, observing the norms and rules of English-speaking communication. Students' comments on the content of the case are evaluated by the teacher on the following skills: analytical, managerial, decision-making skills, interpersonal communication skills, creativity, oral and written communication skills in English (lexico-grammatical aspect). Therefore, the case method includes at the same time a special type of educational material and special ways of using it in the teaching practice of the English language.

According to the results of applied research, it has been established that the case method can be used as extremely effective in achieving the goals of teaching a professional foreign

² Himes, D. (2012). "Competence and Efficiency in Linguistic Theory", in R. Huxley and E. Ingram (eds.) *Language Acquisition: Bed Models*. New York: Academic Press, P.281.

³ Gudakova E.V., Nikulina N.Yu. Modern information technologies as a way to improve the quality of teaching English

// Science Time. - 2014. - No. 7 (7). -P. 87-91.

language and intercultural adaptation. However, the use of this method in teaching a foreign language should be methodologically substantiated and ensured. This is necessary both at the level of organizing the educational process for the educational program as a whole, and at the level of planning it by an individual teacher. The disadvantages of using this method of organizing training include the fact that it is difficult to guarantee the independence of the performance of all tasks in the case of individual students.

The case method in foreign language classes is recommended to be used in groups with a certain stock of knowledge in the specialty and a sufficient level of foreign language proficiency. In addition, being a complex and effective teaching method, the case method is not universal and is effective only in combination with other methods of teaching foreign languages, because. does not in itself constitute a mandatory normative knowledge of the language. Nevertheless, the use of the case method in the study of a foreign language increases the level of knowledge of a foreign language in general⁴.

The method develops creative thinking; develops presentation skills; develops the ability to lead a discussion, argue answers; improves the skills of professional reading in a foreign language and information processing; teaches to work in a team and develop a collective solution. Under the conditions of interactive learning, students increase their sense of personal involvement in the educational process and form responsibility for their own educational results. Discussion, analysis of real situations, brainstorming, business game, project task lead to the creation of a favorable psychological atmosphere in the classroom, to the strengthening of the speech and intellectual activity of students, increase their sense of self-confidence and create a semantic context of communications.

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